

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF EDUCATIONAL TRIPS TO ZOOS IN DEVELOPING FOREIGN LANGUAGE SKILLS AND IMAGINATION IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Ganieva Shahlo Abdukakhor kizi

Shakhrisabz state pedagogical institute

Email: shahloganieva95@gmail.com

Tel: 97-799-95-01

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the effectiveness of teaching English and Russian to 5-6 years old children in a trip to the zoo. It is also stated that the use of "main maps" affects positively children's perception of information, the development of their imagination and the formation of "creative thinking" skills.

Key words: Zoo, the leading action, trip, peculiarity, memory, feelings, imagination, main map, creative thinking, ability, digital economy.

The importance of teaching foreign languages to children cannot be overstated. In the world today, scientific knowledge and information are predominantly communicated in English. The vast majority of academic journals and publications are written in English, and many academic collaborations occur across international borders. Therefore, it is essential to have a strong command of English to keep abreast of scientific advancements, participate in global collaborations, and share our own research findings with the international community. This is why starting language learning at an early age is crucial to achieving the best possible outcomes.

According to D.B. Elkonin's concept of psychological age, imaginative play is the leading activity for children aged 5-6. This is the period when they primarily rely on visual-figurative thinking. It is, therefore, beneficial to utilize these characteristics when teaching foreign languages. Engaging children directly as participants in a scenario or story, allows for a more vivid and memorable learning experience. Research shows that 72 hours later, only 10% of information acquired through listening alone is retained, compared to 65% of information learned through a combination of seeing, hearing, and active participation. Furthermore, when learning is accompanied by positive emotions and sensory experiences, the transfer of information from short-term to long-term memory is accelerated. From this perspective, teaching foreign languages through travel-themed lessons can be highly effective. Furthermore,

- Such lessons offer an opportunity to integrate knowledge from multiple subjects. For example, a trip to Shahrishabz Zoo can combine learning about the animal kingdom with learning English and Russian.
- The experience of seeing live animals in a travel-themed lesson creates lasting memories, as information is absorbed with passion through all sensory channels.
- Travel-themed lessons also provide an opportunity to introduce children to concepts of the environment and ecology, fostering their understanding of these topics. They serve as a unique form of physical exercise as children engage in exploration. Moreover, children can learn the names of animals in Uzbek, English, and Russian:

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Айиқ-а bear-медведь 2. Шер – a lion – лев 3. Бўри- a wolf – волк 4. Тулки – a fox – лиса 5. Туя –a camel – верблюд 6. Куён- a rabbit – кролик 7. Буғу – a deer – олень 8. Илон – a snake – змея 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 9. Тошбақа – a tortoise – черепаха 10. Бургут – an eagle – орел 11. Лочин – a falcon-сокол 12. Туяқуш – an ostrich – страус 13. Товус – a peacock - павлин 14. Чиябўри – red-wolf – шакал 15. Калтакесак – a lizard - ящерица 16. Эчки – a goat – козёл
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The learning process continues within the educational institution. To reinforce what they have learned, children are shown pictures or videos of the animals they saw during the trip, helping them recall their experiences. To further solidify their knowledge, “mind maps” (MM) - a highly effective method of foreign language learning - can be employed. The human brain processes information presented in the form of a mind map, a visual diagram, better than it processes information presented as a list (like the names mentioned above)..

Mind maps (MM) allow students to group information in a visually appealing way, making it easier for them to retain the names in long-term memory. There are other advantages to using mind maps. It is known that the right hemisphere of the human brain is responsible for spatial organization, colors, and emotions. Activation of the right hemisphere promotes the development of imagination and the formation of creative thinking elements. Therefore, students are asked to create simple mind maps using colored pencils. This encourages: 1) Strong emotions in children. 2) A creative competition among students, where each student strives to make their mind map visually appealing. The best mind map is rewarded. 3) The use of colors and the placement of animals on the mind map activates the right hemisphere of the brain. 4) Drawing colorful pictures of the animals along with their names on the mind map reinforces information in long-term memory.

Creating mind maps digitally can be even more effective. This is because, in our current era of “digital economy,” it encourages children to develop their computer skills and fosters an understanding of the importance of mind mapping for both education and life. Below is a sample mind map depicting animals seen at the zoo, categorized by their species.

To further enhance the effectiveness of mind mapping in travel-themed lessons, a role-playing scenario can be developed based on the mind map. This can add another layer of engagement for the children.

Implementing travel-themed lessons would be beneficial for elementary school students as well as older students, of course, taking into account their respective curriculums.

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